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Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Maurizio Avella, Roberto Avolio, Rachele Castaldo, Mariacristina Cocca, Francesca De Falco, Emilia Di Pace, Maria E. Errico, Gennaro Gentile (CNR) Sonia Albein Urios (AIMPLAS) Joan Bellver (BELLVER) Lisa Hoeflechner (TOMRA) Emilie Bossane (FCBA) Markku Vilkki (CONENOR) Sergio Guerri (ITENE) Daniele Spinelli (NTT)
Reviewers (Org)	Dominik Jasinski, Felipe Cicaroni (EXERGY)
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Acronyms and abbreviations

MBW	Municipal bulky waste
ELV	End-life vehicles
EOL	End of life
PE	Polyethylene
HF	Heavy fraction
MF	Medium fraction
LF	Light fraction
CDW	Construction and demolition wastes
FW	Furniture waste
WTB	Wind turbine blade
GFRP	Glass fiber reinforced polymers
BM	Ball milled
FTIR	Fourier-transform InfraRed
ATR	Attenuated Total Reflectance
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
EDX	Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
TG	Thermogravimetric
RH	Relative humidity
UF	Urea-formaldehyde
MF	Melamine-formaldehyde
PP	Polypropylene
PVC	Polyvinylchloride
PA	Polyamide
ABS	Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
GPC	Gel permeation chromatography
RV	Retention volume
PLA	Poly(lactic acid)
PCL	Poly(ϵ -caprolactone)
PBSA	Poly(butylene succinate-co-butylene adipate)

1 Introduction

This report describes the results obtained through the collection of materials from MBW and ELV, the analytical protocol adopted for their characterization and the results obtained from this activity, and the lab-scale tests performed to obtain recycled samples from these materials.

This report is organized as follows.

- Description of the origin of the collected waste materials
- Description of the treatments performed on the collected waste materials
- Protocol of analysis on the collected materials and obtained results
- Lab-scale tests to demonstrate the recyclability of materials from MBW and ELV
- Recommendations for the reprocessing/recycling of the collected waste materials

This report will provide feeds to the following Tasks and Subtasks:

- To Subtasks 2.4.2/3/4/5 regarding intermediate material supply to the various industries specified;
- To WP4 in relation to the properties of materials in view of their remanufacturing/recycling;
- To WP6 in relation to the data generation about EOL materials in view of their remanufacturing/recycling;
- To WP7 for the design and optimisation of the whole circular supply chain, the life cycle assessment and the cost-benefit analysis;
- To WP10, for the environmental risk assessment for the reprocessed materials.

2 Collected materials from MBW and ELV

2.1 Collected materials from MBW

The first class of MBW samples have been collected by TOMRA and delivered to CNR for the characterization.

Two set of samples have been delivered to CNR.

The heavy fraction (HF) is constituted by large wooden pieces, with irregular shape and weight. The medium fraction (MF) is mainly constituted by highly contaminated small wooden pieces, with irregular shape and weight.

Once received by CNR, wooden samples have been coded, weighted, imaged with a digital camera and stored in PE bags. Codes, mass values and images of collected MBW samples are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1 – Codes, mass values and images of MBW samples provided by TOMRA (HF)

Codes	Mass (g)	Image	Notes
TW-HF-1	459.21		Dimensional range 65-325 mm Inorganic contamination (not very significant) Absence of metal parts Absence of plastic contaminants
TW-HF-2	82.15		
TW-HF-3	104.22		
TW-HF-4	169.78		
TW-HF-5	300.25		
TW-HF-6	97.47		
TW-HF-7	346.87		
TW-HF-8	196.61		
TW-HF-9	118.63		
TW-HF-10	96.08		
TW-HF-11	90.04		
TW-HF-12	86.18		
TW-HF-13	87.47		
TW-HF-14	237.35		

Table 2 – Codes, mass and images of MBW samples provided by TOMRA (MF)

Codes	Mass (g)	Image	Notes
TW-MF-1	10.82	<p style="text-align: center;">— 125 mm</p>	<p>Dimensional range 10-65 mm</p> <p>Samples constituted by highly contaminated paper/cardboard (samples 13, 14, 16, 18)</p> <p>Particleboard samples (samples 12,15)</p> <p>Large glue contamination (sample 3)</p> <p>Metal contamination (sample 7)</p> <p>Presence of textile fibers (sample 1)</p>
TW-MF-2	6.83		
TW-MF-3	23.75		
TW-MF-4	23.72		
TW-MF-5	10.68		
TW-MF-6	34.50		
TW-MF-7	8.15		
TW-MF-8	6.72		
TW-MF-9	3.83		
TW-MF-10	7.45		
TW-MF-11	7.64		
TW-MF-12	0.85		
TW-MF-13	0.82		
TW-MF-14	0.22		
TW-MF-15	1.30		
TW-MF-16	0.08		
TW-MF-17	0.74		
TW-MF-18	0.04		

Other wooden MBW samples have been delivered to CNR by CONENOR. In particular, these samples are listed in the following Table.

Table 3 – Codes, mass and images of wooden MBW samples provided by CONENOR

Codes	Mass (g)	Image	Notes
CDW	89.0	<p data-bbox="676 927 949 958">50 mm</p>	Construction and demolition waste
FW	72.0	<p data-bbox="676 1288 949 1319">50 mm</p>	Furniture waste

For what concerns FW, they have been collected by FCBA and obtained in the present form by grinding of different furniture waste: mainly particleboards, plywood, fibreboards, and solid/soft wood.

2.2 Collected materials from ELV

Light fractions of ELV samples (simply coded as ELV) have been collected by GBP on their industrial plants and delivered to CNR for the characterization and to AIMPLAS for pretreatments. About 200 g of ELV have been provided to CNR for characterization and higher amount of ELV to AIMPLAS for pretreatments.

ELV samples´ have been obtained using the following process. EOL vehicles are brought to scrapyards where they are decontaminated and deregistered, before being smashed and shredded into irregular pellets of about 3 mm size. This lightweight fraction contains different plastics and a miscellaneous of foam, textiles, rubber, glasses, and tiny copper

threads. The main problem to be faced for this class of shredded wastes is that a reliable technology on market to automatically separate the different materials is still missed. Another problem is the need of purity that the market requires for their reuse/recycling. In particular, the presence of different plastics in a waste stream is considered one of the most relevant barriers to the recycling, so that different separation technologies are currently under investigation [1].

A digital image of the ELV sample is reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Image of the light fraction of ELV collected by GBP

2.3 Wind turbine blade (WTB) wastes

A relevant class of materials for which different EOL scenarios are the subject of recent researches [2,3,4] is constituted by WTB wastes, mainly constituted by glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRP). During the project implementation milled WTB waste samples have been delivered to CNR by CONENOR. Details on the samples provided are reported in the following table.

Table 4 – Code, mass and image of WTB waste samples provided by CONENOR

Codes	Mass (g)	Image	Notes
WTB	68.8		Wind turbine blade waste

3 Pretreatments of samples

3.1 MBV samples

3.1.1 TW-HF samples

The heavy fraction of the wooden MBW (TW-HF) samples provided by TOMRA was treated at CNR to collect samples for analysis and to perform a size reduction.

In particular, wooden samples TW-HF-1, TW-HF-2, TW-HF-3 and TW-HF-4 were first cut to smaller pieces (< 5 cm).

Some samples were taken apart for the characterization described in the next Section 4.

About 2 kg of the sample were milled by a Retsch SM100 cutting mill equipped with a 2 mm diameter hole bottom sieve. The powder obtained, coded as TW-HF-2mm, was used to evaluate their reusability/recyclability, as described in the next Section 6.

About 200 g of the milled TW-HF-2mm sample were dried in oven at 90 °C under vacuum for 24 h and then treated in a Fritsch Pulverisette 7 planetary micro mill system. For each batch TW-HF-2mm samples of 10.0 ± 0.1 g were milled using stainless steel 80 mL grinding bowls and 25 steel spheres, 10 mm diameter. The weight ratio spheres/ TW-HF-2mm was about 10:1. The ball milling process was carried out for 60 min at 600 rpm. The powder obtained, coded as TW-HF-BM, was used to evaluate their reusability/recyclability, as described in the next Section 6.

3.1.2 Other samples

As concerning TW-MF, CDW and FW samples, these were characterized as received, without any pretreatment.

3.2 ELV samples

ELV samples have processed by AIMPLAS to separate different fractions.

For the pretreatment for ELV samples AIMPLAS applied different methods which are detailed in Deliverable D5.4.

Going to the key of this section, the methodology used to better separate the small fraction obtained from the end of different treatment steps of automotive sector was as follows.

The stream is the ELV 3 mm granulometry mix, described in Section 2.2, apparently composed of different materials (different polymers, textile fibers, copper). So, first of all, an equipment called Zig-Zag air separator has been used, whose image is reported in Figure 2. Thank to this technology, two main different fractions, a heavy one (HM) and a lighter fraction (LM) have been obtained.

Indeed, the main purpose of this process is to separate light fractions from others even lighter. The ELV material with sizes between 2 and 3 mm is conveyed into the zig-zag-shaped sifter channel through an airtight feed mechanism. After that, the lighter materials are separated from heavier ones using a multiple cross-flow sifting process. The air required for this separation process flows from bottom to top through the sifting channel. The lighter particles are swept away with the air current while heavier particles fall toward the bottom against the flow of air and are discharged at the base of the separator.

Figure 2 – Image of the Zig-Zag air separator

As a second step, AIMPLAS has used a metal separator to remove the small fibres of copper in order to obtain a cleanest final sample to be analysed and possibly recycled. AIMPLAS has performed this second pretreatment using the Sesotec Rapid Vario-FS equipment that works detecting the metallic parts (ferrous or no-ferrous materials) and rejecting them from the rest of the sample.

As a result, separated HM-ELV and LM-ELV fractions have been obtained and sent to CNR.

As a further process, AIMPLAS has also pelletized part of the sample, for possible reuse/recycling of the ELV. Pellets of ELV fractions are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Final ELV pellets obtained.

3.3 WTB waste samples

As concerning the WTB waste sample, this was characterized as received, without any pretreatment.

4 Protocol of analysis of MBW samples and obtained results

4.1 Tomra wood (TW) samples

4.1.1 FTIR analysis

Fourier Transform-Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy is a reliable and cost-effective analytical tool for identification of different materials, such as lignocellulose and plastic materials, and the assessment of their purity in view of recycling processes. For instance, FTIR spectroscopy easily allow the identification of binders in wooden products as well as the presence of different plastics in waste mix.

For this reason, attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier-Transform InfraRed (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy analysis was carried out on wooden pieces cut from specimens listed in Tables 1 and 2, as well as on milled wooden samples (TW-HF-2mm and TW-HF-BM), using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum One FTIR spectrometer equipped with the Universal ATR accessory, using 64 scans and a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , over the range $4000\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Before the analysis, samples were conditioned at $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 50% relative humidity (RH) for 24 h.

ATR-FTIR spectra of TW-HF samples are reported in the following Figures.

Figure 4 – ATR-FTIR spectra of samples TW-HF-1, TW-HF-2, TW-HF-3 and TW-HF-4

Figure 5 – ATR-FTIR spectra of samples TW-HF-5, TW-HF-6, TW-HF-7, TW-HF-8 and TW-HF-9

Figure 6 – ATR-FTIR spectra of samples TW-HF-10, TW-HF-11, TW-HF-12, TW-HF-13 and TW-HF-14

FTIR analysis of TW-HF clearly demonstrates the lignocellulosic nature of all the samples, with a strong and complex absorption band in the region $900\text{-}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, typical of the cellulose fraction [5]. Several samples show the presence of polymeric binders, possibly urea-formaldehyde (UF) resins, as demonstrated by adsorption bands typical of $\text{C}=\text{O}$

stretching of amides centred at 1635-1660 cm^{-1} , and N-H stretching centred at 3340-3360 cm^{-1} (TW-HF-2bis, TW-HF-3, TW-HF-4, TW-HF-7, TW-HF-9, TW-HF-11) [6]. To be noted is that the presence of inorganic contaminants, especially silicate contaminants would be masked by the large absorption bands typical of the lignocellulosic fraction.

ATR-FTIR spectra of TW-MF samples are reported in the following Figures.

Figure 7 – ATR-FTIR spectra of samples TW-MF-1, TW-MF-2 and TW-MF-3

Figure 8 – ATR-FTIR spectra of samples TW-MF-4, TW-MF-5, TW-MF-6 and TW-MF-7

Figure 9 – ATR-FTIR spectra of samples TW-MF-8, TW-MF-9, TW-MF-10 and TW-MF-11

Figure 10 – ATR-FTIR spectra of samples TW-MF-12, TW-MF-13, and TW-MF-14

Figure 11 – ATR-FTIR spectra of samples TW-MF-15, TW-MF-16, TW-MF-17 and TW-MF-18

FTIR analysis of TW-MF also demonstrate the lignocellulosic nature of all the samples, with a strong and complex absorption band in the region $900\text{-}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, typical of the cellulose fraction.

Moreover, the presence of large contamination is evident. In particular, polyester fibers are revealed in Figure 7 (TW-MF-1-textile) [7], as shown by strong C=O absorption bands at 1711 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the C=O of the ester groups, by the bands in the region of $1500\text{-}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, corresponding to C-C stretch in aromatic ring and by absorption bands in the region of $1300\text{-}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, typical of C-O stretching of ester groups [8]. The large presence of polymeric glue (possibly polyvinylacetate) in TW-MF-3-glue is also evidenced, as shown by the strong acetate ester carbonyl band at 1728 cm^{-1} , the absorption band at 1127 cm^{-1} , typical of the C-O stretching, and the band centred at 830 cm^{-1} , typical of the C-O-C in-plane bending [9].

Furthermore, UF resins, typical of wooden panels, is evidenced by the presence of adsorption bands typical of C=O stretching of amides centred at $1635\text{-}1660\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and N-H stretching centred at $3340\text{-}3360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (almost all the TW-MF samples, except for TW-MF-2 and TW-MF-4 for which the presence of these bands is not clearly detectable). To be remarked is that absorption bands typical of UF resins are also present in paper samples.

As described in Section 3, some samples from the heavy fraction of the wooden MBW (TW-HF) samples provided by TOMRA were milled to homogenise them and to perform further characterizations. In particular, milled TW-HF-2mm, and ball-milled TW-HF-BM were also investigated by FTIR analysis. Results are reported in the next Figures.

a

b

Figure 12 – ATR-FTIR spectra of samples TW-HF-2mm and TW-HF-BM in the wavenumber range 600-4000 cm^{-1} (a) and enlarged view of the wavenumber range 700-1400 cm^{-1} (b)

As clearly shown, the homogenization of the samples hides the presence of contaminants, whose presence is not clearly detectable in the FTIR spectrum of milled HF samples.

Moreover, to be remarked is that the ball milling sample shows a partial amorphization of the cellulose fraction, as demonstrated by the reduction of the intensity of the absorption bands centred at 1112, 1150 and 1320 cm^{-1} [5].

4.1.2 SEM/EDX analysis

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) combined with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) is a fundamental tool, used in this activity to investigate the morphology and to analyze the elemental composition of the selected waste materials in view of their recycling.

In particular, SEM analysis was performed using a FEI Quanta 200 FEG environmental SEM (ESEM) in low vacuum mode ($P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 80 \text{ Pa}$), using a Large Field Detector (LFD) and an accelerating voltage ranging between 15 and 20 kV. Before the analysis, samples were mounted on aluminium stubs by means of carbon adhesive disks.

EDX analysis was performed on the above described SEM using an Oxford Inca Energy System 250 and an Inca-X-act LN2-free analytical silicon drift detector. EDX analysis was carried out using the point selection mode or the area selection mode. The accelerating voltage was fixed to 30 kV for EDX analysis. For analysis carried out in the area-selection mode, average results and standard deviation values are based on at least 5 consecutive measurements on different areas of the samples.

Representative SEM images of TW-HF samples are reported in the following Figure.

Figure 13 – SEM images of different areas of the sample TW-HF-1

Figure 13a shows the complex morphology of the wooden sample, whereas Figure 13b allows to evidence the presence of a compact layer on some areas of the sample. These areas were analysed by EDX and results are reported in the next Table.

Table 5 – Results of EDX analysis (wt%) on different areas of the sample TW-HF-1

Element	Sample TW-HF-1 – external surfaces similar to Figure 11a	Sample TW-HF-1 – external surfaces similar to Figure 11b
C	48.04 ± 2.34	27.7 ± 1.41
O	46.67 ± 1.04	49.7 ± 2.08
Mg	0.17 ± 0.10	0.52 ± 0.16
Al	0.73 ± 0.35	2.55 ± 0.63
Si	1.92 ± 0.89	7.02 ± 1.73
S	0.81 ± 0.05	3.39 ± 0.10
K	0.17 ± 0.03	0.84 ± 0.09
Ca	1.27 ± 0.07	6.65 ± 0.09
Fe	0.22 ± 0.05	1.58 ± 0.18

The solid layer observed at the surface of some samples can be therefore identified as compacted soil/dust particles. Further SEM images representative of the samples TW-HF are reported in the following Figures, showing different level of contamination.

Figure 14 – SEM images representative of the samples TW-HF showing contamination by the presence of inorganic salts

Figure 15 – SEM image representative of the samples TW-HF showing contamination by the presence of a compact layer of soil

Figure 16 – SEM image representative of the samples TW-HF showing different contaminations

From the large inhomogeneity of the samples, it is evident that to evaluate the average composition of the sample a homogenization process is needed.

As discussed in Section 3, some samples from the heavy fraction of the wooden MBW (TW-HF) provided by TOMRA were milled to homogenise them and to perform further characterizations. In particular, milled TW-HF-2mm, and ball-milled TW-HF-BM were also investigated by FTIR analysis. Results are reported in the next Figures.

Figure 17 – SEM images of the samples TW-HF-2mm

Figure 18 – SEM images of the samples TW-HF-BM

These samples were analysed by EDX and results are reported in Table 5.

Table 6 – Results of EDX analysis (wt%) on different areas of samples TW-HF-2mm and TW-HF-BM

Element	Sample TW-HF-2mm	Sample TW-HF-BM
C	50.58 ± 0.92	50.44 ± 1.32
O	48.67 ± 0.96	49.01 ± 1.29
Mg	0.04 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.02
Al	0.10 ± 0.06	0.08 ± 0.03
Si	0.14 ± 0.08	0.10 ± 0.06
S	0.08 ± 0.05	0.05 ± 0.03
K	0.07 ± 0.05	0.04 ± 0.02
Ca	0.29 ± 0.12	0.22 ± 0.07
Fe	0.03 ± 0.02	0.03 ± 0.02

As shown, the amount of inorganic contaminants observed in milled samples is much lower with respect to those reported in Table 4, showing that contaminants, mainly located at the surface of wooden pieces, are only slightly relevant with respect to the total mass of the organic fraction.

4.1.3 TG-FTIR evolved gas analysis

To investigate the thermo-oxidative stability of the materials and to determine the evolved gases during a thermal treatment in view of their recycling, thermogravimetric (TG) analysis in air flow combined to FTIR analysis of the evolved gases was carried out using a TG-FTIR apparatus. In particular, a thermogravimetric analyser Perkin Elmer Pyris 1 was coupled to a PerkinElmer Spectrum™ Frontier spectrometer by a TL 8000 transfer line with a 10 cm gas cell. The transfer line and gas cell were heated to 270 °C to avoid condensation of organic compounds. Approximately 5 mg of sample were placed in a platinum crucible and heated at a rate of 10 °C/min over a range of 50–800 °C. The purge gases through the TGA was artificial air at a flow rate of 25 ml/min with a balance purge of 45 ml/min. This combined rate of 70 ml/min was kept constant through the transfer line and cell. The FTIR was configured to continuously collect background-corrected spectra over a wave number range of 4000–650 cm⁻¹ for the complete duration of the temperature program at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

The TG curve of the sample TW-HF is reported in the following Figure.

Figure 19 – TG curve of the sample TW-HF in the temperature range 100-750 °C

As shown, the degradation of the sample occurs in two steps, associated with the difference in degradation rate of the cellulose/hemicellulose components (less thermally stable) and the lignin, which in turn degrades slowly over a wide range of temperature [10].

To investigate the processability of the sample as a filler in polymer composites, i.e. the approach proposed in the Ecobulk project, what is relevant is the analysis of the gas evolution at the first stage of degradation, occurring close to the common processing temperatures of polymer composites.

The analysis of the TG curve shows that, after a weight loss due to water evaporation, occurring until about 120 °C, the TW-HF sample starts to decompose at about 220 °C, with a 2 wt% weight loss occurred at about 240 °C.

The analysis of the evolved gases demonstrates that until 320 °C, corresponding to the maximum degradation rate of the first degradation step, mainly carbon dioxide is emitted. This is consistent to what reported in literature for different wood samples [11].

The FTIR spectrum of the evolved gases at 260 °C, typical carbon dioxide spectrum, is shown in the next Figure.

Figure 20 – FTIR spectrum of the evolved gases from the sample TW-HF at 260 °C during TGA

4.1.4 Water content

The water content of TW-HF was investigated by a gravimetric method. In particular, about 10 g of TW-HF were weighed after the grinding treatment and then dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 24 h and weighed again. The recorded weight loss, that represents the water content of the sample, was found 3.2 wt%.

Moreover, to determine the equilibrium water content of the sample, another batch of about 10 g was conditioned at 25 °C and 50% RH for 24 h. The conditioned TW-HF sample was weighed, then dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 24 h and weighed again. The recorded weight loss, that represents the water content of the sample at the reported conditions, was found 12.6 wt%.

4.2 Construction and demolition waste (CDW) sample

4.2.1 FTIR analysis

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy analysis was carried out on CDW as detailed in Section 4.1.1. ATR-FTIR spectra of representative CDW samples are reported in the following Figures.

Figure 21 – ATR-FTIR spectra of representative CDW samples

The sample is almost homogeneous, with small differences amongst FTIR spectra collected on different CDW particles. FTIR analysis well demonstrates the lignocellulosic

nature of all the samples, with the typical cellulose complex absorption band in the region 900-1200 cm^{-1} .

4.2.2 SEM/EDX analysis

The wooden nature of the CWD samples is confirmed by SEM analysis, carried out using the conditions detailed in 4.1.2, and whose results are reported in the following Figure. As shown in most of the SEM images, CWD also contains considerable amounts of a partially defibrillated fibrous contaminant.

Figure 22 – SEM images of CDW samples

Results of EDX analysis on this sample are reported in the following Table.

Table 7 – Results of EDX analysis (wt%) on the CDW sample

Element	Amount (wt%)
C	50.24 ± 2.69
O	49.19 ± 2.85
Si	0.10 ± 0.04
S	0.11 ± 0.08
Ca	0.17 ± 0.04
Cu	0.18 ± 0.10

As shown, the amount of inorganic contaminants is not very relevant, although the presence of copper should be taken into account in view of the recycling process as copper can catalyse the degradation of polyolefins [12].

4.2.3 TG-FTIR evolved gas analysis

TG-FTIR evolved gas analysis was carried out on the CDW sample using the same conditions detailed in 4.1.3. The TG curve of the CDW sample is reported in the following figure.

Figure 23 – TG curve of the sample CDW in the temperature range 100-750 °C

As shown, the TG curve is very similar to that recorded for TW-HF, confirming the wooden nature of the CDW sample. A slightly higher residue at 750 °C is recorded for CDW (about 1.12 wt%).

The analysis of first step of degradation shows that, after a weight loss due to water evaporation, occurring until about 120 °C, the CDW sample starts to decompose at about 220 °C, with a 2 wt% weight loss occurred at about 235 °C.

Similarly to what found for TW-HM, the analysis of the evolved gases from the CDW sample during combustion demonstrate that until 327 °C, corresponding to the maximum degradation rate of the first degradation step, mainly carbon dioxide is emitted.

The FTIR spectrum of the evolved gases at 260 °C, typical carbon dioxide spectrum, is shown in the next Figure.

Figure 24 – FTIR spectrum of the evolved gases from the sample CDW at 260 °C during TGA

4.2.4 Water content

The water content of the CDW sample was investigated by a gravimetric method. In particular, about 10 g of CDW were weighed as received and then dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 24 h and weighed again. The recorded weight loss, that represents the water content of the sample, was found 0.51 wt%.

Moreover, to determine the equilibrium water content of the sample, another batch of about 10 g was conditioned at 25 °C and 50% RH for 24 h. The conditioned CDW sample was weighed, then dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 24 h and weighed again. The recorded weight loss, that represents the water content of the sample at the reported conditions, was found 3.2 wt%.

4.3 Furniture waste (FW) sample

4.3.1 FTIR analysis

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy analysis was carried out on FW as detailed in Section 4.1.1. ATR-FTIR spectra of representative FW samples are reported in the following Figures.

FTIR analysis revealed that the sample is quite homogeneous, with small differences amongst FTIR spectra collected on different FW particles. Nevertheless, as shown in the FTIR spectrum FW_d in the previous Figure, the presence of binders and/or faced layer typical of wooden panels is evidenced.

Figure 25 – ATR-FTIR spectra of representative FW samples

4.3.2 SEM/EDX analysis

The wooden nature of the FW samples is confirmed by SEM analysis, carried out using the conditions detailed in 4.1.2, and whose results are reported in the following Figure. As shown in the SEM images, FW is mainly constituted by wooden particles of variable size (from a few mm to tenth of μm) obtained from the grinding of different wood waste present in furniture: mainly particleboards, plywood, fibreboards, and solid/soft wood.

Figure 26 – SEM images of FW samples

Results of EDX analysis on this sample are reported in the following Table.

Table 8 – Results of EDX analysis (wt%) on the FW sample

Element	Amount (wt%)
C	48.13 ± 1.62
O	46.91 ± 0.92
Si	0.90 ± 0.16
S	1.17 ± 0.44
Cl	0.41 ± 0.08
K	0.48 ± 0.08
Ca	1.78 ± 0.30
Fe	0.21 ± 0.12

As shown, the overall amount of inorganic contaminants is lower than 5 wt% and it could be compatible with the recyclability of the sample. Nevertheless, the presence of some large inorganic particles (lateral dimension about in the mm range) is also to be evidenced, as shown in the next Figure, and it should be taken into account for the reprocessing of the sample.

Figure 27 – SEM image and results of EDX analysis carried out on the selected area of the FW sample

4.3.3 TG-FTIR evolved gas analysis

TG-FTIR evolved gas analysis of the FW sample was carried out using the same conditions detailed in 4.1.3. The TG curve of the FW sample is reported in the following Figure.

Figure 28 – TG curve of the sample FW in the temperature range 100-750 °C

Also in this case a two-step degradation process is observed, with a higher residue at 750 °C (about 2 wt%) with respect to TW-HF and CDW. Despite to their similar wooden nature, the FW sample shows an anticipated degradation with respect to TW-HF and CDW, the sample starting to decompose at about 225 °C (about 2 wt% weight loss) and the maximum degradation rate of the first decomposition step occurring at 316 °C.

The Gram-Schmidt profile of FW is reported in the following Figure. The point corresponding to the temperature of 225 °C (about 2 wt% weight loss) is marked in the curve.

Figure 29 – Gram-Schmidt profile of the FW sample

The corresponding FTIR spectrum is reported in the next Figure. As shown, apart CO₂ absorption bands, new bands appear, typical of isocyanic acid, HCNO, marked in blue, and NH₃, marked in red. These emissions have been already evidenced and analysed during pyrolysis and combustion of urea-formaldehyde resins [13]. As furniture wastes are

typically constituted by different types of wood boards containing urea-formaldehyde binders, the emission of these substances is not surprising in this sample. To be also underlined is that these emissions are significant also as temperatures as low as 220 °C, very close to processing conditions of polymer composites. Moreover, if FW are used as fillers in polymer matrices, shear forces occurring during processing, more relevant in presence of rigid fillers, can induce local increases of the temperature that can reach values even higher than 220 °C also if the processing temperature was set at lower values.

All these results clearly indicate that the reprocessing of FW must be carefully designed to prevent harmful emissions that could affect the safety of the working environments and of the final products.

Figure 30 – FTIR spectrum of the gases evolved from FW at 225 °C in air

4.3.4 Water content

The water content of the FW sample was investigated by a gravimetric method. In particular, about 10 g of FW were weighed as received and then dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 24 h and weighed again. The recorded weight loss, that represents the water content of the sample, was found 0.61 wt%.

Moreover, to determine the equilibrium water content of the sample, another batch of about 10 g was conditioned at 25 °C and 50% RH for 24 h. The conditioned FW sample was weighed, then dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 24 h and weighed again. The recorded weight loss, that represents the water content of the sample at the reported conditions, was found 3.9 wt%.

5 Protocol of analysis of ELV samples and obtained results

5.1 Preliminary analysis on ELV

Digital images of the ELV sample, collected under LED illumination on a Lynx Evo stereomicroscope, are reported in the following Figure.

Figure 31 – Digital images of ELV waste samples

As shown, the sample seems to be mainly constituted by plastic particles with lateral dimension close to 3 mm and it shows a large number of impurities, such as metal elements and fibers.

SEM/EDX analysis, performed using the same environmental conditions detailed in 4.1.2, confirmed the presence of metal impurities and fibers. In the next Figures (a and b) the surface of a polymer particle and some fibers are respectively reported, mainly constituted by carbon and oxygen. Instead, as indicated in the Figures c and d, metal impurities are mainly constituted by copper wires and steel particles. Moreover, particles constituted by glass fiber reinforced composites have been also evidenced (Figure e).

Figure 32 – Results of SEM/EDX analysis of ELV sample

To investigate the contamination by inorganic or metal elements, a representative amount of ELV was thermally treated at 800 °C for 2 h, under air atmosphere, to remove most of the organic component. The weight residual was found about 25 wt%. EDX analysis performed on the powder obtained at the end of the thermal treatment, after mechanical homogenization, revealed the composition reported in the following table.

Table 9 – Results of EDX analysis (wt%) on the residue at 800 °C of the sample ELV

Element	Amount (wt%)
C	26.98 ± 4.36
O	50.70 ± 2.61
Na	0.59 ± 0.02
Mg	4.20 ± 0.59
Al	2.00 ± 0.01
Si	7.80 ± 1.21
S	0.72 ± 0.01
Cl	1.10 ± 0.34
K	0.12 ± 0.01
Ca	3.27 ± 0.62
Ti	0.33 ± 0.05
Cr	0.02 ± 0.01
Fe	0.27 ± 0.04
Cu	1.03 ± 0.05
Zn	0.62 ± 0.02
Ba	0.26 ± 0.01

The chemical composition of the ELV sample before the thermal treatment is not reported because the large inhomogeneity of the sample prevented the obtainment of a reliable EDX analysis.

Results reported in table 9 indicate that the main non-organic contaminants of the ELV sample are possibly glass fibers (as shown by the high presence of Si in the residual) and copper elements, while the presence of steel, randomly evidenced by SEM/EDX analysis, is almost negligible.

With the objective of identifying the nature of the polymer particles, several particles were randomly selected and characterized by FTIR analysis, using the same experimental conditions detailed in 4.1.1. FTIR spectrum of the polymer particles are reported in the following Figure.

Figure 33 – FTIR spectra of randomly selected ELV particles

FTIR spectra a and b demonstrate the presence of polypropylene (PP) [14]. Spectrum c is typical of polyamide 6 [15]. Spectra d, h and i are typical of an acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene resin [16]. Finally, spectra e, f, g and j, with the typical bands at 1435 and 610 cm^{-1}

(CH₂ wagging and C-Cl stretching, respectively) and the ester C=O stretching bands at about 1730 cm⁻¹, typical of common plasticizers, are indicative of plasticized polyvinylchloride (PVC) [17, 18] that seems one of the main constituent of the ELV sample.

Finally, ELV particles undergone Soxhlet extraction in chloroform [19] for 12 h to evaluate the amount of plasticizers and low molecular weight substances. The procedure gave a 21 wt% weight reduction after extraction, indicating the large presence of plasticizers (either from PVC either from other polymeric materials) and additives soluble in the selected solvent.

5.2 Characterization of HM-ELV and LM-ELV

After the separation procedure adopted by AIMPLAS, in view of ELV recycling, the ELV sample were separated into the two batches denoted as HM-ELV and LM-ELV (see Section 3.2). These batches were fully characterized using the analytical methods detailed in the following sections.

5.1.1 Density separation test

First, a density separation test [20] was performed on the HM-ELV and LM-ELV by treatment of the samples with a NaCl saturated solution at 25 °C (density 1.20 g/cm³). In particular, to 20.0 g of HM-ELV or LM-ELV a volume of 400 mL of the brine NaCl solution was added and the mixture was stirred at 300 rpm for 5 minutes. The magnetic stirrer was lifted from the solution and the rinsed with a small amount of saturated NaCl solution. The solution was left to settle for 20 minutes, allowing the lighter particles to float or stay in suspension as the heavier sediment particles sank. The particles that accumulated on the surface of the solution were recovered by using a steel strainer. The remaining particles were recovered by filtration and rinsed with distilled water. The same procedure was repeated on a different sample with distilled water (density 1.00 g/cm³).

After rinsing and drying at 60 °C under vacuum overnight, the different fractions recovered by each experiments were weighed. In this way, the amounts of floating fractions of each sample in water, with density < 1.00 g/cm³, was calculated (A). Similarly, the floating fraction in the brine NaCl solution with density < 1.20 g/cm³ (B), and the remaining fraction in the same solution, with density ≥ 1.20 g/cm³ (C), were obtained. Results are reported in the following table.

Table 10 – Results of density separation tests on LM-ELV and HM-ELV

Sample	d < 1.00 g/cm ³ (A) amount (wt%)	d ≥ 1.20 g/cm ³ (B-A) amount (wt%)	d ≥ 1.20 g/cm ³ (C) amount (wt%)
LM-ELV	9.8	63.0	27.0
HM-ELV	0	9.1	90.9

Comparing these results with density data of polymeric materials [21], it is expected that PE fractions (HDPE and LDPE) and PP copolymers fall in the low density fraction, reinforced PP, PA6, PA11, ABS, PS and some PVC flexible filled particles fall down in the intermediate fraction, whereas most of the flexible PVC, PET, most of the glass fiber reinforced components and metal impurities fall in the higher density fraction.

5.1.2 Extraction in chloroform and GPC of the extracted phase

Similarly to ELV, HM-ELV and LM-ELV samples undergone Soxhlet extraction in chloroform for 12 h to evaluate the amount of plasticizers and low molecular weight substances. The procedure gave the results reported in the following table, in which results obtained for ELV are also reported by comparison.

Table 11 – Results of the extraction procedure in chloroform on ELV samples

Sample	Amount of the fraction extracted on chloroform (wt%)
ELV	21.0
LM-ELV	17.9
HM-ELV	25.1

As shown, the HM-ELV sample is the most rich in plasticizers and soluble phases extracted in chloroform.

The extracted phases were then analysed by gel permeation chromatography (GPC). More in detail, GPC analysis was performed using a GPC Max Viscotek system equipped with a TDA 305 triple detector (Refractive Index, Low Angle Light Scattering, Right Angle Light Scattering and Viscometer), a UV detector and Phenomenex Phenogel columns: a precolumn and two columns respectively of 10^6 and 10^3 g/mol. All the samples were dissolved and eluted in chloroform stabilized with ethanol (chloroform HPLC Grade, Sigma Aldrich). After complete dissolution, they were filtered on PTFE membranes of 0.22 μm . The injection volume was 100 μl , the flow rate 0.8 ml/min and the sample concentrations about 5 mg/ml. The chosen method of analysis was triple point, calibrated with a PS standard, provided by Viscotek, having narrow molecular weight distribution (Mw 105.000 Da, Mw/Mn 1.037). The measurements were performed at 35 °C, according to the temperatures of columns and detectors, for 50 min.

Similar measurements were not performed on the extracted from the ELV sample because of the poor solubility of the extracted phase in cold chloroform.

Chromatograms obtained on LM-ELV and HM-ELV extracted phases are reported in the following Figure and the results are summarized in the next Table.

Figure 34 – GPC chromatograms of the extracted phases in chloroform of LM-ELV and HM-ELV

Table 12 – Results of the GPC analysis of the extracted phases in chloroform of LM-ELV and HM-ELV

Sample	peak	Mn (Da)	Mw (Da)	Mw/Mn	Weight fraction (%)	Inherent viscosity (dL/g)
LM-ELV	1 (low RV)	20738	45398	2.19	40.1	0.3384
	2 (high RV)	572	612	1.07	59.9	0.0308
HM-ELV	1 (low RV)	11034	17473	1.58	12.6	0.6524
	2 (high RV)	298	532	1.78	87.4	0.0525

As shown, either for LM-ELV either for HM-ELV the extracted phases show a high molecular weight component at low retention volumes and a low molecular weight component at higher retention volumes. In both cases, the high molecular weight components are due to polymer fractions soluble in the selected solvent, whereas the low molecular weight components derive from the presence of plasticizers and additives in the ELV fractions.

5.2.3 FTIR analysis of the extracted phases in chloroform

The extracted phases in chloroform from LM-ELV and HM-ELV have been analysed by ATR-FTIR using the experimental conditions described in Section 4.1.1. ATR-FTIR spectra of these extracted phases are reported in the next Figure.

Figure 35 – FTIR spectra of extracted phases in chloroform of samples LM-ELV and HM-ELV

FTIR spectra show absorption bands typical of phthalate plasticizers. Indeed, a research performed using FTIR additive libraries has given as a result for both extracts high overlapping with di-alkyl phthalates (di-n-octyl phthalate or di-isononyl phthalate with more than 97% search score for both LM-ELV and HM-ELV extracted).

Figure 36 – Results of the library search for FTIR spectra of extracted phases in chloroform of samples LM-ELV and HM-ELV: more than 97% search score for common PVC plasticizers, such as di-n-octyl phthalate and di-isononyl phthalate

5.2.4 Characterization of processed LM-ELV and HM-ELV

As shown in the previous sections, the fractions LM-ELV and HM-ELV are still inhomogeneous in terms of composition. For this reason, the composition analysis, performed by ATR-FTIR and EDX, was carried out on processed samples, more homogeneous, prepared as detailed in the next Section 6.2.1. The adopted processing conditions were selected to avoid possible degradation phenomena of the PVC phase possibly present in both the ELV fractions [22].

FTIR analysis was carried out using the same experimental conditions detailed in 4.1.1. FTIR spectra of the LM-ELV and HM-ELV fractions are reported in the following Figure.

Figure 37 – ATR-FTIR spectra of processed LM-ELV and HM-ELV samples

Both ELV spectra show the presence of the several absorption bands of plasticized PVC. Nevertheless, the high intensity of the bands at 2915 and 2848 cm^{-1} and the convoluted, shoulder at 1471 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the processed LM-ELV, indicate the presence of polyethylene.

EDX analysis, performed using the same procedure detailed in 4.1.2, confirmed these results. Indeed, the Cl/C weight ratio was found 0.25 for LM-ELV and 0.42 for HM-ELV, suggesting a lower amount of PVC in the LM-ELV sample. Considering that the Cl/C weight ratio in neat, unplasticized PVC, is 1.476 and assuming that all the chlorine present in the samples is due to PVC, the amount of PVC in LM-ELV and HM-ELV can be calculated by stoichiometric considerations. Results are reported in the following Table 13. To be noted is that the assumption that chlorine is only due to PVC, although formally non-correct (for the possible presence of organic and inorganic chlorinated additives), does not invalidate the approximate quantification of the PVC phase, because of the typical low content of these additives in polymer blends.

Table 13 – Results of EDX analysis of LM-ELV and HM-ELV and approximate quantification of PVC in these samples

Sample	C/C weigh ratio	Approximate content of PVC, without plasticizers (wt%)
LM-ELV	0.25	16.9
HM-ELV	0.42	28.4

5.2.5 TG-FTIR evolved gas analysis

TG-FTIR evolved gas analysis of the HM-ELV and LM-ELV samples was performed using the same experimental conditions reported in Section 4.1.3. The TG curves are reported in the following Figure.

Figure 38 – TG curves of the samples LM-ELV and HM-ELV in the temperature range 100-750 °C

As shown, the TG profiles for the samples are very similar. A weight loss of about 2 wt% is recorded at 200 °C either for LM-ELV either for HM-ELV. The first degradation step is more relevant for the sample HM-ELV, containing a higher amount of PVC fraction with respect to LM-ELV, thus suggesting that this degradation step is attributable to one of the components of plasticized PVC.

FTIR spectra of evolved gases from both samples at 200 °C are reported in the following Figure. As shown, CO₂ is present in both samples, together with a component whose FTIR spectrum is very similar to a phthalate plasticizer, whose spectrum is reported for comparison. Moreover, the presence of hydrochloric acid is also evidenced by the presence of the absorption bands in the 2600-3200 cm⁻¹ region.

Figure 39 – FTIR spectra evolved gases from LM-ELV and HM-ELV samples at 200 °C curves under air flow. The spectra of a phthalate plasticizer and hydrochloric acid are reported for comparison

Therefore, for both LM-ELV and HM-ELV emissions are significant also as temperatures as low as 200 °C and start to be detectable also at about 190 °C. These results clearly indicate that the recycling of LM-ELV and HM-ELV should be carefully designed and investigated to avoid harmful emissions during processing, keeping the processing temperatures and the emissions under strict control.

Indeed, the wrong selection of the processing conditions could lead to the emission of harmful gases, mainly hydrochloric acid and phthalates, both very harmful by inhalation [23, 24, 25]

5.2.6 Water content

The water content of the ELV samples was investigated by a gravimetric method. In particular, about 10 g of ELV was weighed as received and then dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 24 h and weighed again. The recorded weight loss, that represents the water content of the sample, was found 1.25 wt%.

Conditioning at 25 °C and 50 % RH of the pre-dried sample and test repetition gave a water content lower than 0.1 wt%, demonstrating the low hydrophilic nature.

6 Wind turbine blade (WTB) waste

6.1 FTIR analysis

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy analysis was carried out on WTB waste as detailed in Section 4.1.1. ATR-FTIR spectra of representative WTB samples are reported in the following Figures.

Figure 40 – ATR-FTIR spectra of representative WTB waste samples

FTIR analysis revealed that the sample is quite homogeneous, with no significant differences amongst spectra collected on different WTB waste particles. FTIR analysis indicates that WTB results constituted by a vinylester resins [26] reinforced with glass fibers.

6.2 SEM/EDX analysis

Representative SEM images of the WTB waste sample are reported in the following Figure. SEM images clearly show the presence of isolated glass fibers as well as fiber bundles still embedded in the polymer matrix.

Figure 41 – SEM images of WTB waste samples

Results of EDX analysis on this sample are reported in the following Table.

Table 14 – Results of EDX analysis (wt%) on the WTB waste sample

Element	Amount (wt%)	Element	Amount (wt%)
C	omitted	Cl	0.597 ± 0.219
O	70.857 ± 0.383	K	0.207 ± 0.015
Na	0.457 ± 0.077	Ca	6.806 ± 0.247
Mg	0.394 ± 0.011	Ti	0.180 ± 0.089
Al	4.469 ± 0.039	Fe	0.698 ± 0.056
Si	14.954 ± 0.238	Ni	0.007 ± 0.004
S	0.307 ± 0.199	Cu	0.067 ± 0.021

In this analysis, the quantification of carbon has been omitted to better identify the presence of other elements. As shown, several elements constitute the sample, mainly due to the presence of glass fibers. Comparing the results of EDX with data reported in literature [27], glass fibers have been identified as E-glass.

6.3 TG-FTIR evolved gas analysis

TG-FTIR evolved gas analysis of the WTB sample was carried out using the same conditions detailed in 4.1.3.

Figure 42 – TG curves of the WTB sample in the temperature range 100-750 °C

As shown, the TG profiles indicates a very high residual weight at 750 °C, mainly due to the presence of glass fibers, although the recorded residual weight is not able to indicate the exact amount of the inorganic component in the composite due to the inhomogeneity of the sample and the low amount of material that can be investigated by TG analysis. Moreover, a weight loss of about 2 wt% is recorded at 245 °C whereas the maximum degradation rate occurs at 339 °C.

As shown in the following Figure, mainly water and carbon dioxide are evolved during the first degradation stages, up to 280 °C, whereas other organic elements are evolved during the main degradation step, starting at about 300 °C. This result indicates that the analysed grinded WTB wastes can be safely used as rigid fillers by processing at the typical temperatures used for the compounding of thermoplastic polymers. Nevertheless effective precautions must be planned in the working environments because of the presence of free fiberglass in the WTB sample, as shown by morphological analysis and a deep analysis of

the materials realized should be performed to exclude the release of fiberglass during the use of the realized products.

Figure 43 – FTIR spectra evolved gases from WTB waste at 280 °C under air flow.

6.3.1 Water content

The water content of the WTB waste samples was investigated by a gravimetric method. In particular, about 10 g of WTB was weighed as received and then dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 24 h and weighed again. The recorded weight loss, that represents the water content of the sample, was found lower than 0.01 wt%.

Conditioning at 25 °C and 50 % RH of the sample and test repetition gave a similar result, demonstrating the low water content of the sample also after moisture conditioning.

7 Recyclability tests

7.1 Recyclability tests of MBW samples

7.1.1 Recyclability tests of TW samples

With the objective of demonstrating the recyclability of heavy fraction of the wooden MBW (TW-HF) samples provided by TOMRA, TW-HF was milled to obtain two different fractions, namely TW-HF-2mm and TW-HF-BM, as detailed in the Section 3.1.1. These milled TW-HF fractions were then tested as reinforcing fillers in polymer based composites using a commercial PLA polymer matrix. The realization of the composites was carried out using the process conditions detailed below [28, 29, 30]. To be remarked is that the size reduction of a cellulose based filler by planetary ball milling was an approach already tested by the CNR group for the realization of polymer biocomposites based on PCL or PBSA with functional properties, such as a faster biodegradation kinetic in comparison to the neat matrix [31, 32].

PLA/TW-HF composites were prepared by melt mixing in a Brabender Plastograph internal mixer at 185 °C for 10 min at 64 rpm mixing speed. Two kinds of composites were prepared through the following procedures.

- Plain composites. They were obtained by melt mixing of PLA and TW-HF-2mm or TW-HF-BM using the following weight ratio between the components: PLA/TW-HF-2mm and PLA/HF-TW-BM 85/15 and 70/30.
- Composites containing a coupling agent. The coupling agent, coded as CA, was a PLA modified by grafting with maleic anhydride, obtained at CNR as described in [28]. Materials were prepared using the following weight ratio between the components: PLA/CA/TW-HF-2mm and PLA/CA/HF-TW-BM 63/7/30.

Samples were then pelletized and were compression moulded in a Collin P200 laboratory platen press at 190 °C up to a final pressure of 200 bar. The moulded sample were quickly cooled to room temperature by means of a water circulating cooling cassette system and the pressure was released. Sheets (thickness ~ 3.0 mm) were obtained for further characterizations.

Neat PLA was processed using the same conditions and used as a reference.

Codes and compositions of the realized materials are reported in the following table. Images of the obtained samples are reported in the next Figure.

Table 15 – Codes and compositions of PLA based composites containing TW-HF

Codes	PLA (wt%)	CA (wt%)	TW-HF-2mm (wt%)	TW-HF-BM (wt%)
PLA	100	0	0	0
PLA/TW 85/15	85	0	15	0
PLA/TW 70/30	70	0	30	0
PLA-CA/TW 70/30	63	7	30	0
PLA/TWBM 85/15	85	0	0	15
PLA/TWBM 70/30	70	0	0	30
PLA-CA/TWBM 70/30	63	7	0	30

Figure 44 – Images of the surfaces of the obtained PLA based composites containing TW

A mechanical analysis has been performed on the obtained samples. In particular, the flexural strength and the flexural modulus of the samples were measured in a three-point bending mode using an Instron machine (model 5564), at a cross-head speed of 5 mm/min and at 25 °C and 50 % RH. Before the analysis samples were conditioned for at

least 24 h. Test specimens were about 3 mm thick, 10 mm wide, and 70 mm long. The test span was 48.0 mm. For each sample, 6 specimens were tested, and the average and standard deviation values of the flexural strength and modulus were calculated.

Results of mechanical analysis of PLA based composites containing TW-HF are reported in the next Table.

Table 16 – Results of mechanical analysis of PLA based composites containing TW-HF

Codes	Flexural modulus (MPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)
PLA	2960 ± 95	92.8 ± 2.4
PLA/TW 85/15	3755 ± 130	73.2 ± 3.2
PLA/TW 70/30	4475 ± 100	65.9 ± 4.1
PLA-CA/TW 70/30	4280 ± 260	74.9 ± 2.8
PLA/TWBM 85/15	3260 ± 105	79.6 ± 3.9
PLA/TWBM 70/30	3735 ± 110	73.3 ± 5.2
PLA-CA/TWBM 70/30	3790 ± 110	78.7 ± 3.1

Results demonstrate that, despite the presence of low amount of inorganic contaminants, the TW-HF waste are suitable for their use in polymer based composites. The size of the wood particles significantly affect the final properties of the materials, with large wood particles being more effective to increase the modulus of the final composites. Moreover, very small size of the wooden particles, such as those obtained by planetary ball milling, induce a less detrimental effect on the flexural strength of the composites. In any case, the presence of a coupling agent is useful to improve the interfacial adhesion between the polymer matrix and the filler, thus reducing the decrease of the flexural strength of the final materials.

7.1.2 Recyclability tests of CDW and FW samples

The recycling process of CDW and FW and WTB samples has been reported in the Deliverable D3.1 Report on development of the intermediate materials for composite production. In particular, CDW and FW and WTB have been used by CONENOR for the realization of several classes of products through agglomeration technology. For a detailed discussion of the obtained materials and corresponding properties, please refer to D3.1 - Section 4, where:

- construction and demolition wood waste (CDW) are detailed in D3.1-Section 4.3.1;

- furniture wastes (FW) are those provided by FCBA and detailed in D3.1-Section 4.3.1;

To be remarked is that the results of the analytical protocol adopted in this document, and in particular the analysis of evolved gases during thermal treatments demonstrate that the conditions adopted for the agglomeration process described in D3.1 are suitable for the CDW. Also for FW the low temperature agglomeration conditions described in D3.1 (for all samples lower than 175 °C) are safe, although in this case the process needs a strict temperature control to prevent the release of harmful substances.

7.2 Recyclability tests of ELV samples

7.2.1 Preparation of the samples

About 50 g of each of the LM-ELV and HM-ELV samples were processed in a Brabender Plastograph internal mixer at 160 °C for 10 min at 15 rpm mixing speed. Successively, the obtained materials were compression moulded in a Collin P200 laboratory platen press at 170 °C up to a final pressure of 200 bar. The moulded sample were quickly cooled to room temperature by means of a water circulating cooling cassette system and the pressure was released. Sheets (thickness ~ 3.5 mm) were obtained and used for ATR FTIR and EDX characterization.

Figure 45 – Images of the surfaces of the sheets LM-ELV and HM-ELV

The obtained samples have been analysed by tensile tests. Results are reported in the next Table and they demonstrate that the large presence of different immiscible polymer phases prevent the obtainment of good mechanical properties for both the LM-ELV and the HM-ELV fraction. Further activities are needed to improve the purity of the obtained fractions in order to obtain recycled products characterized by better mechanical properties.

Table 17 – Results of mechanical analysis of recycled products prepared from LM-ELV and HM-ELV

Codes	Young modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
LM-ELV	360 ± 30	1.87 ± 0.42	5.6 ± 0.4
HM-ELV	19.5 ± 2.0	1.31 ± 0.39	26.9 ± 5.1

7.3 Recyclability tests of WTB waste samples

The recycling process of WTB samples has been reported in the Deliverable D3.1 Report on development of the intermediate materials for composite production. In particular, WTB have been used by CONENOR for the realization of several classes of products through agglomeration technology. For a detailed discussion of the obtained materials and corresponding properties, please refer to D3.1 - Section 4, where:

- wind turbine blade are those provided by VIROL and described in D3.1-Section 4.3.2.

To be remarked is that the results of the analytical protocol adopted in this document, and in particular the thermo-oxidative stability and the analysis of evolved gases during thermal treatments clearly demonstrate that the conditions adopted for the agglomeration process described in D3.1 are suitable for the selected WTB wastes.

8 Recommendations for the recycling of MBW, ELV and WTB wastes

As shown in the previous sections, all waste samples selected in the Ecobulk project are very complex and heterogeneous materials containing different impurities. These substances are resumed in the following Table and they can represent possible serious obstacles toward a safe and cost-effective recycling of the selected MBW, ELV and WTB wastes.

Table 18 – Different impurities evidenced in the selected MBW, ELV and WTB waste samples

Selected wastes	Main constituents	Most relevant Impurities
MBW	Wood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - plastic contaminants - metal contaminants - paper contaminants - inorganic contaminants (soil, dust) - binders (UF resins, MF resins)
ELV	PVC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - non-PVC plastics - plasticizers - metal contaminants - inorganic additives - GFRP
WTB	GFRP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no extraneous substances detected

In particular, depending on their origin, wood MBW show different levels of contamination.

The heavy fraction of wood collected by TOMRA on their industrial sorting plants (TW-HF) mainly shows the presence of soil and dust contamination, whose relative amount is very low and does not preclude the direct recycling of the wood particles as a filler in polymer composites after appropriate grinding.

Similarly, construction and demolition wastes (CDW) provided by CONENOR, show an acceptable level of contamination, although in this case some metal contaminants (such as copper) must be taken into account in view of the recycling of CDW wooden particles as a filler in polymer composites after appropriate grinding.

A different situation must be underlined for furniture wastes (FW), constituted by wooden particles obtained by grinding of different products typically used in the furniture sector,

such as particleboards, plywood, fibreboards, and solid/soft wood. Most of these products contain binders whose thermal stability is only partially compatible with their recycling as fillers in polymer composites. For these materials, the evolved gas analysis showed the emission during thermal treatments of different substances, such as isocyanic acid and ammonia. These emissions are typical of pyrolysis and combustion of urea-formaldehyde resins, typically used as binders in furniture elements. Unfortunately these emissions are significant also at temperatures as low as 220 °C, in some cases close to processing conditions of polymer composites. Moreover, if FW are used as fillers in polymer matrices, shear forces occurring during processing, more relevant in presence of rigid fillers, can induce local increases of the temperature that can reach values even higher than 220 °C also if the processing temperature was set at lower values. All these results indicate that the reprocessing of FW must be carefully designed to prevent harmful emissions that could affect the safety of the working environments and of the final products.

For what concerns the analysed ELV samples, they are constituted by shredded plastic particles containing different amounts of metal impurities, depending on the separation technology adopted. The plastic fraction of these samples is mainly constituted by plasticized PVC, mixed to other polymers, such as polyolefins and ABS resins. The direct reprocessing of the ELV samples does not produce a recycled material with satisfactory properties, mainly because of the presence of several immiscible polymer fractions. Moreover, some of the polymer components present in the ELV sample remain unmelted during the processing of ELV that must be carried out at relatively low temperatures to prevent emission of harmful substances such as phthalates and hydrochloric acid. For this class of wastes, more effective sorting technologies should be developed to separate and thus reprocessing the PVC fraction.

Finally, the analysis of a particular class of wastes, namely shredded wind turbine blade (WTB) samples obtained by the dismantling of wind turbines, revealed that they are mainly constituted by fiberglass reinforced thermosetting polymer particles, containing large amounts of free fiberglass fragments produced during grinding. The activities performed during Ecobulk implementation have demonstrated that WTB wastes can be effectively recycled by using them as fillers in polyolefins through agglomeration technologies. In this case, effective precautions must be planned in the working environments because of the presence of free fiberglass in the WTB sample, and a deep analysis of the materials realized must be performed to exclude the release of fiberglass during the life of the realized products.

8.1 Concluding remarks

The activities performed to characterize MBW, ELV and WTB wastes have shown how an appropriate analytical protocol can contribute to evaluate the reprocessability of different classes of wastes and to select the appropriate reprocessing conditions to ensure a safe and effective recycling.

As a general recommendation, a deep chemical characterization is needed, to investigate the chemical nature of the main constituents of the selected waste streams and the contaminants. For this purpose FTIR spectroscopy is very useful to determine the chemical nature of the materials and elemental analysis (such as EDX) is able to reveal the presence on inorganic and metal contaminants. This analytical protocol is essential to evaluate the recyclability of the selected waste streams or to plan further sorting/purification steps before recycling.

Moreover, to properly select the reprocessing conditions, the analysis of the thermal stability of the material is a fundamental step to determine if the selected processing temperatures are suitable for the selected class of wastes, in order to prevent the emission of harmful substances during the recycling process. In particular, thermogravimetric analysis coupled to the analysis of the evolved gases is very important to determine the possible emission of harmful volatile substances. Therefore, once designed a recycling process, a preliminary TG-evolved gas analysis should be considered mandatory to ensure the safety and to select appropriate precaution measures in the working environments.

Finally, all the new materials realized by the reuse of wastes should be deeply analysed to evaluate the possible migration and release of hazardous substances and to evaluate the fate and the environmental impact of the new products during their use, disposal and further recycling [33].

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